

FREE EDGE ANALYSIS OF CFRP LAMINATES BASED ON A HOMOGENIZATION THEORY FOR TIME-DEPENDENT COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The homogenization theory based on a unit cell analysis [1] is useful for analyzing mechanical properties of microscopically periodic materials such as composites, because it can analyze not only their macroscopic behavior but also the microscopic stress and strain fields in them. In this theory, first, a periodic material is considered and its unit cell is defined. Then, its macroscopic and microscopic properties can be analyzed by applying the theory to the unit cell. So far, a lot of microscopically periodic materials, mainly composite materials [2-5], are analyzed based on the theory.

This theory, however, requires the assumption that materials possess infinite periodic structures microscopically. This means that this theory cannot be applied to a free edge analysis of composites. On the other hand, at free edges, characteristic deformation and stress and strain distributions which are different from that of an internal area of materials may occur. These are sometimes called the 'edge effect', and can cause microscopic failure such as microscopic cracks. Such failure can bring about macroscopic fracture of composites. Thus, it is extremely important to analyze microscopic stress and strain distributions around free edges.

The authors already carried out an elastic-viscoplastic analysis [6], an interlaminar stress analysis [7,8], a creep analysis [9] and a misaligned internal structure analysis [10] of CFRP laminates based on a homogenization theory for nonlinear time-dependent materials [11]. These analyses showed that microscopic stress and strain concentrations can occur at the interfaces, such as fiber/matrix and lamina/lamina interface regions in CFRP laminates. However, these analyses were based on the conventional homogenization theory which was developed for infinite periodic materials. Thus, these were not able to deal with the edge effect of CFRP laminates. The free edge analysis for CFRP laminates is necessary because CFRP laminates used for industrial products inevitably have free edges in reality. It is therefore useful to

develop a homogenization theory applicable to the free edge analysis.

In this study, a homogenization theory for time-dependent composites with free edges is newly proposed. This theory is then applied to the analysis of microscopic stress and strain distributions at the free edges of a unidirectional CFRP laminate subjected to a macroscopic load. From the analysis results, microscopic stress and strain concentrations at fiber/matrix interface regions around the free edges are examined.

2 Theory

2.1 Modeling of Unidirectional CFRP Laminate

In this study, a unidirectional CFRP laminate with free edges subjected to a macroscopic uniaxial load in the $y_2 - y_3$ plane is considered (Fig. 1). The laminate has an infinite length in the y_2 - and the y_3 -directions, while it has a finite length in the y_1 -direction. This laminate is reinforced in the y_1 -direction, and the fibers are arranged squarely in the $y_2 - y_3$ plane for simplicity. Then, a unit cell Y for the laminate including the free edges is defined as shown in Fig. 1.

2.2 Homogenization Theory for Free Edge Analysis

Describing microscopic distributions of stress and strain in Y as $\sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, t)$ and $\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, t)$, respectively, the equilibrium of σ_{ij} can be expressed as

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij,j} = 0, \quad (1)$$

where (\cdot) and $(\cdot)_{,i}$ denote the differentiation with respect to t and y_i , respectively. Constituents of the material are assumed to exhibit linear elasticity and nonlinear viscoplasticity as characterized by

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijkl}(\dot{\varepsilon}_{kl} - \beta_{kl}), \quad (2)$$

where c_{ijkl} and β_{ij} indicate the elastic stiffness and the viscoplastic strain rate of the fibers and the

Fig. 1. Unidirectional CFRP laminate with free edges and unit cell Y .

matrix, respectively. In addition, c_{ijkl} and β_{ij} satisfy the following relations:

$$c_{ijkl} = c_{jikl} = c_{ijlk} = c_{klij}, \quad (3)$$

$$\beta_{ij} = \beta_{ji}. \quad (4)$$

The microscopic velocity field $\dot{u}_i(\mathbf{y}, t)$ in Y has the following expression:

$$\dot{u}_i(\mathbf{y}, t) = \dot{\mathbf{F}}_{ij}(t)y_j + \dot{u}_i^\#(\mathbf{y}, t), \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{F}_{ij} indicates the macroscopic deformation gradient, $\dot{u}_i^\#$ stands for the perturbed velocity field from the macroscopic one $\dot{\mathbf{F}}_{ij}(t)y_j$. Then the microscopic strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ is expressed as a sum of the macroscopic strain rate \dot{E}_{ij} and the perturbed strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\#$, i.e.,

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, t) = \dot{E}_{ij}(t) + \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\#(\mathbf{y}, t), \quad (6)$$

where \dot{E}_{ij} and $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\#$ satisfy the following relations:

$$\dot{E}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(\dot{\mathbf{F}}_{ij} + \dot{\mathbf{F}}_{ji}), \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\# = \frac{1}{2}(\dot{u}_{i,j}^\# + \dot{u}_{j,i}^\#). \quad (8)$$

Then, the integration by parts and the divergence theorem allow Eq. (1) to be transformed to

$$\int_Y \dot{\sigma}_{ij} v_{i,j} dY - \int_\Gamma \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma = 0. \quad (9)$$

In the above equation, Γ denotes the boundary of Y , $v_i(\mathbf{y}, t)$ indicates an arbitrary variation of $u_i^\#(\mathbf{y}, t)$, n_i stands for the unit vector outward normal to Γ . Now, let us consider the second term of the left-hand side in Eq. (9), i.e. the boundary integral term. First, on the internal surfaces, boundary Γ_A , $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and v_i

satisfy the Y -periodicity, while n_i takes opposite directions on opposite boundary facets. Thus, the boundary integral term of Γ_A becomes

$$\int_{\Gamma_A} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_A = 0. \quad (10)$$

Next, on the free edges, boundary Γ_B , the in-plane components of $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and v_i satisfy the Y -periodicity. Therefore, the boundary integral term with respect to the in-plane components becomes zero from the same reason as for the internal surfaces

$$\int_{\Gamma_B} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_B = 0, \quad (ij = 22, 33, 23). \quad (11)$$

In contrast, the Y -periodicity of the out-of-plane components is no longer satisfied at the free edges. However, no traction force works along the out-of-plane direction at the free edges. Thus, the following relation can be derived:

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = 0 \quad (ij = 11, 12, 31). \quad (12)$$

Thus, the out-of-plane components of the boundary integral term result in

$$\int_{\Gamma_B} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_B = 0, \quad (ij = 11, 12, 31). \quad (13)$$

From Eqs. (11) and (13), the boundary integral term of Γ_B also becomes

$$\int_{\Gamma_B} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_B = 0. \quad (14)$$

Consequently, the boundary integral term of Eq. (9) vanishes, and Eq. (9) is rewritten as

$$\int_Y \dot{\sigma}_{ij} v_{i,j} dY = 0. \quad (15)$$

Equation (15) has the same form as that obtained from the conventional homogenization theory for time-dependent composites [11]. Substitution of Eqs. (2) and (6) into Eq. (15) results in

$$\int_Y c_{ijpq} \dot{u}_{p,q}^{\#} v_{i,j} dY = -\dot{E}_{kl} \int_Y c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} dY + \int_Y c_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} v_{i,j} dY. \quad (16)$$

Equation (16) has the following solution for $\dot{u}_i^{\#}$:

$$\dot{u}_i^{\#}(\mathbf{y}, t) = \chi_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}) \dot{E}_{kl}(t) + \varphi_i(\mathbf{y}, t). \quad (17)$$

In Eq. (17), χ_i^{kl} and φ_i denote the characteristic functions determined by solving the boundary value problems as follows:

$$\int_Y c_{ijpq} \chi_{p,q}^{kl} v_{i,j} dY = -\int_Y c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} dY, \quad (18)$$

$$\int_Y c_{ijpq} \varphi_{p,q} v_{i,j} dY = \int_Y c_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} v_{i,j} dY, \quad (19)$$

where χ_i^{kl} has the following relation:

$$\chi_i^{kl} = \chi_i^{lk}. \quad (20)$$

The evolution equation of microscopic stress σ_{ij} and the relation between macroscopic stress rate $\dot{\Sigma}_{ij}$ and strain rate \dot{E}_{ij} are derived as follows:

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijpq} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \dot{E}_{kl} - c_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \varphi_{k,l}), \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{\Sigma}_{ij} = \left\langle c_{ijpq} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \right\rangle \dot{E}_{kl} - \left\langle c_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \varphi_{k,l}) \right\rangle, \quad (22)$$

where δ_{ij} indicates Kronecker's delta, and $\langle \# \rangle$ designates the volume average in Y defined as

$$\langle \# \rangle = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y \# dY, \quad (23)$$

in which $|Y|$ signifies the volume of Y . Here, $\dot{\Sigma}_{ij}$ is defined as

$$\dot{\Sigma}_{ij} = \left\langle \dot{\sigma}_{ij} \right\rangle. \quad (24)$$

Then applying Eq. (23) to Eq. (6) and considering the Y -periodicity of $\dot{u}_i^{\#}$, \dot{E}_{ij} is defined as

$$\dot{E}_{ij} = \left\langle \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \right\rangle. \quad (25)$$

The boundary value problems, Eqs. (18) and (19), in a finite element discretized form are derived as follows:

$$\mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\chi}^{kl} = \mathbf{F}^{kl} \quad (kl=11, 22, \dots, 31), \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\varphi} = \mathbf{G}, \quad (27)$$

where \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{F}^{kl} and \mathbf{G} have the following expressions:

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_Y \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{B} dY, \quad (28)$$

$$\mathbf{F}^{kl} = -\int_Y \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C}^{kl} dY, \quad (29)$$

$$\mathbf{G} = \int_Y \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\beta} dY. \quad (30)$$

From Eq. (21), microscopic stress distribution in the vicinity of the free edges of the unidirectional CFRP laminate subjected to a macroscopic load can be analyzed. When solving Eqs. (18) and (19), the ordinary Y -periodic boundary condition is imposed on the internal surfaces, while the combination of the Y -periodic and the traction-free boundary conditions is imposed on the free edges.

3. Numerical Analysis Techniques

3.1 Semiunit Cell

Let us consider half of the unit cell Y as illustrated in Fig. 2, which hereafter is referred to as a semiunit cell \tilde{Y} . A close look at Fig. 2 reveals that the internal structure of the laminate has a point-symmetry with respect to the center of the left boundary facet of \tilde{Y} , point C. Consequently, the distributions of the characteristic functions χ_i^{kl} and φ_i also satisfy the point-symmetry with respect to this point. Using the point-symmetry as a boundary condition on the left boundary facet, \tilde{Y} instead of Y can be employed as the domain of analysis, leading to the following boundary value problems with respect to \tilde{Y} [12]:

$$\int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijpq} \chi_{p,q}^{kl} v_{i,j} d\tilde{Y} = -\int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} d\tilde{Y}, \quad (31)$$

$$\int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijpq} \varphi_{p,q} v_{i,j} d\tilde{Y} = \int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} v_{i,j} d\tilde{Y}. \quad (32)$$

Equations (31) and (32) can be also expressed as a finite element discretized form as follows:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\chi}}^{kl} = \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{kl} \quad (kl=11, 22, \dots, 31), \quad (33)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varphi}} = \tilde{\mathbf{G}}, \quad (34)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{kl}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{G}}$ also have the following expressions:

Fig. 2. Semiunit cell \tilde{Y} of unidirectional CFRP laminate.

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}} = \int_{\tilde{Y}} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{B} d\tilde{Y}, \quad (35)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{kl} = - \int_{\tilde{Y}} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C}^{kl} d\tilde{Y}, \quad (36)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{G}} = \int_{\tilde{Y}} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\beta} d\tilde{Y}. \quad (37)$$

When solving Eqs. (31) and (32), the point-symmetric boundary condition with respect to C on the left boundary facet, boundary Γ_C , is imposed on χ_i^{kl} and φ_i .

3.2 Substructure Method

Semiunit cell \tilde{Y} is divided into cubic substructures A_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, N$) as shown in Fig. 3. Then the boundary value problems for the individual substructures are expressed as follows [7,8,13]:

$$\mathbf{K}_A \boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl} = \mathbf{F}_A^{kl} \quad (kl=11, 22, \dots, 31), \quad (38)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_A \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i} = \mathbf{G}_{A_i}, \quad (39)$$

where \mathbf{K}_A , \mathbf{F}_A^{kl} and \mathbf{G}_{A_i} have the following expressions:

$$\mathbf{K}_A = \int_{A_i} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{B} dA_i, \quad (40)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_A^{kl} = - \int_{A_i} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C}^{kl} dA_i, \quad (41)$$

Fig. 3. Semiunit cell \tilde{Y} with substructures.

$$\mathbf{G}_{A_i} = \int_{A_i} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\beta} dA_i. \quad (42)$$

It is noteworthy that all A_i have common \mathbf{K}_A and \mathbf{F}_A^{kl} because the geometry and material constants of all A_i are the same. Therefore, it is enough for us to calculate \mathbf{K}_A and \mathbf{F}_A^{kl} only once.

Next, the components of $\boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}$ are respectively divided into two parts, $\boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl(\Gamma)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl(\Omega)}$, and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}^{(\Gamma)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}^{(\Omega)}$, where Γ and Ω indicate the boundary node components and the internal node components of A_i . Then, the boundary value problems for A_i , Eqs. (38) and (39), are rewritten into the following equations, respectively:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Gamma)} & \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Gamma\Omega)} \\ \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega\Gamma)} & \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl(\Gamma)} \\ \boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl(\Omega)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_A^{kl(\Gamma)} \\ \mathbf{F}_A^{kl(\Omega)} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (43)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Gamma)} & \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Gamma\Omega)} \\ \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega\Gamma)} & \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}^{(\Gamma)} \\ \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}^{(\Omega)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{G}_{A_i}^{(\Gamma)} \\ \mathbf{G}_{A_i}^{(\Omega)} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (44)$$

and we obtain

$$\boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl(\Omega)} = (\mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega)})^{-1} (\mathbf{F}_A^{kl(\Omega)} - \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega\Gamma)} \boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl(\Gamma)}), \quad (45)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}^{(\Omega)} = (\mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega)})^{-1} (\mathbf{G}_{A_i}^{(\Omega)} - \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega\Gamma)} \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}^{(\Gamma)}). \quad (46)$$

The elimination of $\boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl(\Omega)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}^{(\Omega)}$ from Eqs. (43) and (44) using the above equations, respectively, yields

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}}_A^{(\Gamma)} \boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl(\Gamma)} = \bar{\mathbf{F}}_A^{kl(\Gamma)} \quad (kl=11, 22, \dots, 31), \quad (47)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}}_A^{(\Gamma)} \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}^{(\Gamma)} = \bar{\mathbf{G}}_A^{(\Gamma)}, \quad (48)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{K}}_A^{(\Gamma)}$, $\bar{\mathbf{F}}_A^{kl(\Gamma)}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{G}}_A^{(\Gamma)}$ are expressed as follows:

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}}_A^{(\Gamma)} = \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Gamma)} - \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Gamma\Omega)} \left(\mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega)} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega\Gamma)}, \quad (49)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_A^{kl(\Gamma)} = \mathbf{F}_A^{kl(\Gamma)} - \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Gamma\Omega)} \left(\mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega)} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{F}_A^{kl(\Omega)}, \quad (50)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{G}}_{A_i}^{(\Gamma)} = \mathbf{G}_{A_i}^{(\Gamma)} - \mathbf{K}_A^{(\Gamma\Omega)} \left(\mathbf{K}_A^{(\Omega)} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{G}_{A_i}^{(\Omega)}. \quad (51)$$

Finally, Eqs. (47) of all substructures are assembled into one equation, which is the boundary value problem with respect to just the boundary nodes of all substructures, which the joint nodes of adjacent substructures belong to:

$$\mathbf{K}^{(\Gamma)} \boldsymbol{\chi}^{kl(\Gamma)} = \mathbf{F}^{kl(\Gamma)}. \quad (52)$$

Moreover, Eqs. (48) of all substructures are also assembled into one equation in the same manner:

$$\mathbf{K}^{(\Gamma)} \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(\Gamma)} = \mathbf{G}^{(\Gamma)}. \quad (53)$$

In the above equations, $\mathbf{K}^{(\Gamma)}$ stands for the matrix consisting of $\bar{\mathbf{K}}_A^{(\Gamma)}$, $\mathbf{F}^{kl(\Gamma)}$ and $\mathbf{G}^{(\Gamma)}$ indicate the vectors consisting of $\bar{\mathbf{F}}_A^{kl(\Gamma)}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{G}}_{A_i}^{(\Gamma)}$, respectively. Moreover, $\boldsymbol{\chi}^{kl(\Gamma)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(\Gamma)}$ denote the nodal vectors of the characteristic functions at the boundary nodes of substructures. The characteristic functions $\boldsymbol{\chi}^{kl(\Gamma)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(\Gamma)}$ are determined by solving Eqs. (52) and (53) with appropriate boundary conditions, i.e., the traction-free, the point-symmetric and the Y -periodic conditions stated in the above subsections, and the continuity condition at the joint nodes of adjacent substructures. Then, the characteristic functions at the internal nodes, $\boldsymbol{\chi}_{A_i}^{kl(\Omega)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{A_i}^{(\Omega)}$, are calculated using Eqs. (45) and (46).

4 Analysis

4.1 Analysis Conditions

Using the present method, microscopic stress and strain distributions in the vicinity of a free edge of a unidirectional CFRP laminate were analyzed. The substructure A_i was discretized into 8-node isoparametric elements as depicted in Fig. 4 (4320 elements and 5005 nodes). The volume fraction of the fibers was 56% [7,8]. The material constants were set as listed in Table 1 [6], where the subscripts L and T indicate the longitudinal and the transverse directions of the fibers, respectively. The fibers were regarded as transversely isotropic elastic materials. On the other hand, the epoxy matrix was assumed to be an isotropic elastic-viscoplastic material obeying the following constitutive equation [6];

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1+\nu}{E} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} - \frac{\nu}{E} \dot{\sigma}_{kk} \delta_{ij} + \frac{3}{2} \dot{\varepsilon}_0^p \left[\frac{\sigma_e}{g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p)} \right]^n \frac{s_{ij}}{\sigma_e}, \quad (54)$$

Fig. 4. Substructure A_i and finite element mesh.

Table 1. Material constants.

	$E_{LL} = 240[\text{GPa}]$	$\nu_{TT} = 0.49$
Carbon fiber	$E_{TT} = 15.5[\text{GPa}]$	$\nu_{LT} = 0.28$
	$G_{LT} = 24.7[\text{GPa}]$	
	$E = 3.5[\text{GPa}]$	$\nu = 0.35$
Epoxy	$\dot{\varepsilon}_0^p = 10^{-5}$	$n = 35$
	$g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p) = 141.8(\bar{\varepsilon}^p)^{0.165} + 10$	

where $g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p)$ denotes a hardening function depending on accumulated viscoplastic strain $\bar{\varepsilon}^p$, $\dot{\varepsilon}_0^p$ indicates a reference strain rate, s_{ij} stands for the deviatoric part of σ_{ij} , and

$$\sigma_e = \left[\frac{3}{2} s_{ij} s_{ij} \right]^{1/2}. \quad (55)$$

The loading condition was a macroscopic constant strain rate $10^{-5} [\text{s}^{-1}]$ in the y_3 -direction.

4.2 Decision of the Number of Substructures in \tilde{Y}

Before performing the free edge analysis, the number of substructures in the semiunit cell \tilde{Y} , N , must be decided because it is an arbitrary parameter. To decide N , the relations between N and the macroscopic and microscopic properties of \tilde{Y} were examined. For example, Fig. 5 is the relation

Fig. 5. Change of macroscopic Young's modulus E_3 .

between the number of substructures N and macroscopic Young's modulus in the loading direction, E_3 . In this figure, the dots show the result of the free edge analysis, while the solid line shows that of the conventional homogenization theory. Figure 5 designates that the interaction between the free edges disappears macroscopically with increase in N , and the result of the free edge analysis converges on that of the conventional homogenization theory. Not only the macroscopic properties but also the microscopic properties, such as the maximum value of microscopic stress in \tilde{Y} , converge with increase in N . Thus, the number of substructures was set at 30 in the following analysis, which is enough to avoid the interaction between the both free edges.

4.3 Analysis Results

4.3.1 Macroscopic Stress-Strain Relation

Figure 6 shows macroscopic stress-strain relations of a unidirectional CFRP laminate under transverse direction tensile load. In this figure, the solid line shows the result of the free edge analysis, while the dots show that of the conventional homogenization theory for time-dependent materials. As seen from this figure, these results show a good agreement with each other, which means that the edge effect scarcely affects the macroscopic properties of a

Fig. 6. Macroscopic stress-strain relations.

Fig. 7. Semiunit cell \tilde{Y} and substructures A_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 30$).

unidirectional CFRP laminate. This indicates that the interaction between the free edges was successfully avoided by setting N at 30.

4.3.2 Microscopic Stress and Strain Distributions

In this analysis, the microscopic stress and strain distributions in the whole semiunit cell \tilde{Y} were obtained. In this subsection, however, the results for the substructures A_1 , A_{29} and A_{30} in \tilde{Y} were selectively shown. As depicted in Fig. 7, A_1 has the point-symmetric surface, A_{29} is one substructure away from the free edge, and A_{30} has the free edge surface, respectively.

Figures 8(a)-(c) show the distributions of microscopic shear stress τ_{31} in A_1 , A_{29} and A_{30} when macroscopic tensile strain is 1.5%, respectively. The deformed shapes of these substructures are also depicted in these figures, where the displacement is magnified 10 times. It is seen from the figures that remarkable microscopic shear stress concentration occurs around the fiber/matrix interface region in the vicinity of the free edge (Fig. 8(c)). The maximum value of τ_{31} reaches 42.3MPa, which is about 38% of the macroscopic tensile stress. However, such stress concentration drastically decreases a little away from the free edge, and shear stress doesn't occur at the internal region of \tilde{Y} (Figs. 8(a) and 8(b)).

Then, Figs. 9(a)-(c) depict the distributions of accumulated viscoplastic strain $\bar{\epsilon}^p$ in the substructures under the same loading condition. Figure 9(c) shows that the maximum viscoplastic strain occurs in the epoxy matrix around the free edge. It is the same region where the maximum shear stress occurred. Macroscopic uniform tensile strain is 1.5%, while the maximum value of $\bar{\epsilon}^p$ is about 3.0%. Thus, the maximum value of microscopic viscoplastic strain is twice as high as macroscopic one. But also in this case, such strain concentration limitedly occurs around the free edge, and the distributions become uniform in \tilde{Y} along the y_1 -direction, i.e. the fiber direction (Figs. 9(a) and 9(b)). These results show that the edge effect has a great influence on the microscopic stress and strain distributions in the vicinity of the free edge, though the influence is quite local.

5. Conclusions

In the present study, a free edge analysis method based on a homogenization theory for time-dependent materials was newly proposed. For this, a traction-free boundary condition instead of periodic boundary condition was applied at free edges of CFRP laminates. And then, using this method, three-

Fig. 8. Distributions of microscopic shear stress τ_{31} in (a) A_1 , (b) A_{29} and (c) A_{30} .

Fig. 9. Distributions of microscopic accumulated viscoplastic strain $\bar{\varepsilon}^p$ in (a) A_1 , (b) A_{29} and (c) A_{30} .

dimensional microscopic stress and strain distributions in the vicinity of a free edge of a unidirectional CFRP laminate were analyzed. It was shown that remarkable microscopic stress and strain concentrations occurred around the fiber/matrix interface region of the free edge. However, such stress and strain concentrations significantly decrease a little away from the free edge. This suggests that it is necessary to pay attention to microscopic stress and strain concentrations caused by the edge effect around free edges of CFRP laminates.

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